

Challenges of Polish Public Administration in the Light of Legal Rules in 2025

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Abstract

The challenges of modern times aggregate previously unseen situations, which forces the intensification of studies on their prevention, containment action and restoration of the desired state. The approach to the challenges of public administration in the light of legal rules in Poland and the resulting need to change public administration through the possibilities provided for by law, in confrontation with the actual state of affairs constitute a plane of research. Three elements come to the fore, which can be listed in the following order: 1. Civilizational incompetence - as a destabilizing concept; 2. Cliques - in the formula of destructive collective social activity deliberately degenerated by the team; 3. Lack of distinction between power and administrative authority leading to delegitimization of law and deprivation of the possibility of its implementation by societies in the public plane combined with dictatorial abuse by the government executive. The concept of public administration remains at a high level of social interest with a simultaneous decrease in public interest when positions in public administration are obtained after elections, implemented in a varied manner in the zone of the so-called Western civilization. At present, i.e. during the writing of this article, many directions of development are visible. The issues mentioned arouse research interests in many fields and scientific disciplines. This article is devoted to the challenges of public administration in the light of legal regulations in Poland.

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Introduction

Western civilization, defined as a complex and dynamic system of values, institutions, and cultural practices, was founded on the foundations of Greek philosophy, Roman law, and Christian morality. This amalgam of cultures has developed a type of critical thinking and an approach to the individual that is reflected in the concepts of human rights, democracy, and science. A fundamental component of Western civilization has become the principle of the so-called separation of powers, which influences the political and social structures in many countries. Key far-reaching values, such as individual autonomy, respect for personal freedom, and the pursuit of social justice, were to shape the ethical code of this civilization. Western civilization is currently facing threats that may threaten its integrity. The decline of democratic values, social polarization, and the growing supply of disinformation are just some of the

symptoms of a broader crisis. In this context, the role of the above-mentioned institution seems crucial, not only as an institution dealing with intelligence, but also in shaping political strategies, which in the last half-century (it is considered that since the end of World War II) have been aimed at protecting the stability of their interests, which are often currently in conflict with obligations towards the governments of the countries that established them, becoming independent in the literal sense, with practically unlimited financial resources (guaranteed by law, as in Poland according to the content of the Act) [1]. The analysis of the actions taken by the above-mentioned entities in the context of the collapse of Western civilization seems to be not only a current topic, but also deeply embedded in the discourse on the future of democratic values of the changing world, and in particular human rights [2]. In this account, it is important to understand how phenomena

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that affect the state of contemporary civilization are interpreted and reacted to, as well as what mechanisms and strategies they implement. Moreover, globalization, confrontation with diverse traditions and the impact of internal crises, such as wars or economic crises, constantly redefine the meaning and scope of the concept of Western civilization, the decline in trust in democratic institutions and growing social inequalities indicate that some foundations of this civilization may be put to the test [3].

The social changes taking place in today's world are contributing to the disintegration of Western civilization by affecting social structures, cultural norms, and interpersonal interactions. The growing sense of alienation resulting from globalization and industrialization, combined with dynamic demographic changes, are laying the foundation for many social problems. Generational differences in attitudes toward values, work, and interpersonal relationships are becoming increasingly evident, leading to the erosion of traditional social bonds. Younger generations, raised in the age of technology, often prefer virtual interactions over personal ones, undermining the importance of local communities and protected traditions. The rise of social movements, representing the pursuit of social justice and equality, and their diverse approaches to issues such as minority rights and economic reformation, reflect a growing frustration with existing systems. As research shows, societies dominated by tensions and divisions are more susceptible to chaos and instability. At the same time, growing cultural diversity, fueled by migration and global exchange, has led to phenomena such as social polarization and radicalization. New group identities emerge, which often challenge established norms and change social dynamics.

Some intellectuals (e.g. Oswald Spengler, Samuel Huntington) point to the cyclical nature of civilization's development and decline; identity crisis, among others due to multiculturalism; weakening of traditional values; declining natural increase; indebtedness of economies; growing competition from China and Russia.

The introduction of Polish public administration in the context of the challenges of 2025 requires reflecting significant changes taking place on many levels, including both in the field of law and in the socio-economic context. Poland, as a member of the European Union, must face EU regulations, which have been dynamically developed in recent years and are changing the way in which public administration functions. Due to the growing complexity of legal issues, the administration creates challenges related to adapting to directives that affect, among others, the topics of environmental policy, migration and digitalization of services. Each of these issues requires analysis and implementation of effective solutions that are aimed not only at meeting legal requirements, but also at satisfying the growing expectations of citizens.

In the interdisciplinary approach, the beginning of the decline of Western civilization is considered to be in the context of the disruption of democratic and non-democratic mechanisms of states on all continents of the Earth, primarily through the activities of the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA), MI6 (Secret

Intelligence Agency). Intelligence Service SIS) and Mossad (Hebrew: Ha-Mosad le-Modi'in u-le-Tafkidim Mejuchadim). In addition to those mentioned, when analysing Poland, we also mention the Internal Security Agency (ABW) and other entities that are not described in detail and operate formally but often in a secret manner, such as the so-called Bilderberg Group [4]. The phenomena studied require an understanding of the complex interactions between social, economic and political factors that shape the contemporary world.

The collapse of Western civilization is a complex issue influenced by internal factors (crisis of values, demographic, economic and others) and external factors (geopolitics, actions of great powers). In this context, the role of intelligence services such as the CIA, Mossad or MI6 and the ABW appears. During a meeting in May 2025 in Antalya, Turkey, Prof. Jeffrey Sachs, a long-time advisor to US Presidents, pointed out, among others, the operation called "Operation Timber Sycamore" informing about the project aimed at implementing 7 wars in 5 years leading to domination of the Middle East by the US and Israel. He indicated Iran as the only war that has not started [5]. This information is now outdated – Israel bombed Iran during Iranian peace talks with the US on Saturday, killing senior officials of that country while they were sleeping and preparing for further talks with the US, when President Donald Trump committed to meeting at the table on Sunday. Analysts assess this action as deliberate misleading of Iran.

As for Poland, the situation finds threads connecting the changes in the country with the activities of the CIA according to the statements of Prof. Jeffrey Sachs (statements on the YouTube program pages) commissioned by the President of the USA in 1988 to the present.

However, the beginning of the interference in Polish affairs by the USA is much earlier. In the 1970s, under the administration of the USSR, the Polish special services, i.e. the Security Service (SB), established contact with the US intelligence agency CIA. The global division was related to the so-called communist system and the so-called democratic system. The CIA was tasked with, among other things, influencing by all possible means and methods to change this balance of power in favor of the USA thanks to projects financed by the US government such as USAID. The CIA's PRL activities found support in the Soviet service in the PRL, i.e. the SB. The training was covered by a secret clause. It was during these that interest was shown in the person of Bishop Macedo (a Brazilian priest) and his achievements, who became the prototype for actions for the Polish equivalent of Tadeusz Rydzyk (posing as a Redemptorist monk) and the aim was to influence the inhabitants of Poland and the Polish diaspora through media investments under the name of TV and Radio Trwam in the formula of religious messages and to establish a school educating political staff. Knowledge was obtained about trade unions and their possibilities in future manipulations. At that time, Poland had a strong industry subordinated to the needs of the USSR, unrelated to internal needs, which in consequence led to liquidation after the launch of the so-called transformation, strictly subordinated to the interests of the USA. The prototype was Jimmy Hoffa [6], an American trade union activist, long-time chairman of the Teamsters union, who came up with the

name for the Union - SOLIDARNOŚĆ - the prototype of later unions in Poland. In the years 1981-1989, Poland was preparing for changes in response to the transformations in the USSR, and the option of the so-called systemic transformation was prepared under direct supervision by the CIA. Martial law in Poland and the so-called internment of 1981 enabled the integration of the management staff of the "Solidarity" trade union with the officers of the Soviet regime in the territory and the removal of Polish patriots inconvenient for the regime from decision-making circles. Internment took place in various facilities, often closed in prisons, where officers of the Polish services and "Solidarity" decision-makers were placed in the same cells without informing who was who. The imprisoned quickly integrated and supported each other, creating frameworks for future political parties and a platform for cooperation with the "Solidarity" Trade Union. A good move for the regime was the promotion to the so-called trade union leader Lech Wałęsa, an agent of the political police, i.e. the Security Service, in domestic and foreign media, and then his nomination by the services for the Nobel Prize (150 signatures on the application for the award). Numerous meetings were held in Poland and abroad, such as the meeting of General Jaruzelski, among others, with Rockefeller in 1985 behind closed doors in the USA. Since then, meetings have also been held with representatives of other European countries with the main participation and under the direction of the CIA, establishing the formulation of a team to manage Poland by selected people and under their direction. The basis for these activities, the model, was the CIA's experience in Chile, where President Salvador Allende was murdered in order to introduce the dictator General Augusto Pinochet, calling this process the "Shock Doctrine". The main elements were unjustified inflation, privatization of banks, industry and its liquidation on a large scale and the formation of a party form with the participation of indicated activists allied with the CIA, i.e. the USA in a permanent manner. The issues of reducing the value of Polish currency were established, adapting it to the needs of hostile takeovers of the economy and banks, as well as the savings of Poles invested not only in banks but also in other financial forms. In fact, in the years from 1990, a process of changes was launched in Poland using the state budget, creating many public institutions, including administration, e.g. at the central level, which are to support maintaining the influence of activists from those years, as well as institutions manipulating public opinion in the form of so-called science for the regime ideology through institutes called scientific and then carrying out annual, secret training with the participation of invited people, modeled on the last official meeting in 2024 in Karpacz [7]. The party system, linked to elections, was organized using a mathematical algorithm, which was the method most often used in the creation of financial pyramids in the USA. In this way, a situation was created in which an individual's vote for the party that receives the most votes translates into a greater number of MPs than the remaining votes, creating a significant inequality that excludes the democratization of this public sphere according to the Constitution of the Republic of Poland in force in Poland [8]. The creation of political parties was financed from USAID funds in such a way as to ultimately lead to the two-party model in force in the USA. By financing artificial political elites, absolute influence was obtained over them, including their political status. This nationwide fraud, combined with numerous actions financing, among others, the

implementation of the 10-point program destabilizing society developed with the participation of the famous US scientist Noam Chomsky: 1. Distract [9]. A key element of social control is the strategy of diverting public attention from important issues and changes made through the technique of constant distraction and accumulation of irrelevant information. The strategy of distraction is also necessary to prevent society from becoming interested in basic knowledge in the field of, among others, democracy, administration, economics, psychology. 2. Create problems, then propose a solution. This method is also called "problem-reaction-solution." It creates a "situation" intended to provoke a reaction in the audience that will demand preventive steps.

For example: create an economic crisis to justify radical cuts to society's rights and the dismantling of social benefits. 3. Gradualize the changes. Acceptance to an unacceptable level. Move the boundaries gradually, step by step, over the next few years. This will enable the provision of minimum benefits, privatization, will cause uncertainty about tomorrow, mass unemployment, low wages, no guarantee of a decent salary - changes that, if introduced at once, would provoke social protests. 4. Delay changes. Another way to induce acceptance of an unwelcome change is to present it as a "painful necessity" and obtain the consent of society to implement it in the future. It is easier to accept a future sacrifice than to submit to it immediately. This is a consequence of the naive tendency to assume that "everything will be fine" and that it may be possible to avoid the sacrifice. 5. Speak to society as to a small child. Most content addressed to the public opinion uses the manner of speech, argumentation or even patronizing tone used when speaking to children or the mentally ill. "If you talk to a person as if he were 12 years old, then, because of the suggestion, the person will most often answer or react uncritically, as if he were really 12 or younger." 6. Focus on emotions, not reflection. Using the emotional aspect is a technique to bypass rational analysis in the individual. The use of emotional speech allows certain ideas, fears and anxieties to be implanted and certain behaviors to be induced. 7. Keep society ignorant and average. Make society incapable of understanding the techniques and methods of control and enslavement. "The education offered to the lower classes must be as poor and average as possible so that the gap of ignorance between the lower and higher classes is incomprehensible to the lower classes." 8. Convince society that it is good to be average. Showing reality more absurd than it really is is a very useful trick. It generates a pleasant emotional reaction – in the face of absurdity, one can feel one's superiority. On the other hand, however, this distorted reality is less and less likely to engage energy to want to change what does not fit. Make society believe that it is "cool" to be stupid, vulgar and uneducated. 9. Replace rebellion with a sense of guilt. Let individuals believe that they are solely to blame for their failures, and this is due to a lack of intelligence, abilities and effort. So instead of rebelling against the political and economic system, the individual will live with a sense of devaluation of their own worth, guilt, which leads to depression, and this leads to inhibition of action. 10. Know people better than they know themselves. Thanks to biology, neurobiology and applied psychology, the "domination system" has achieved advanced knowledge about human beings, both physical and psychological, it knows the individual better than

they know themselves. This means that in most cases it has more control over individuals than individuals have over themselves. Acceptance to an unacceptable level. Move the border gradually, step by step, over the next few years. This will enable the provision of minimum benefits, privatization, will cause uncertainty about tomorrow, mass unemployment, low wages, no guarantee of decent earnings - changes that, if introduced at once, would provoke social protests. When Poland was admitted to the European Union, officials did not inform that they had been changing the laws since 1990. Quietly, but quickly, they sold out the Banks, removing the possibility of national control over the value of money. They acquired property by liquidating industry, leading to bankruptcy or selling it for a small fraction of its value [10]. In 1997, after many disputes, mainly about the preamble, leaving many provisions without consulting the public, the Constitution of the Republic of Poland was validated, creating restrictions on changes to such an extent that it could not be amended. The fact that the EU agreement is one-sided - without the option of opting out - was passed over in silence. Instead, a vision of equality, development through co-investment in industry, agriculture, science, was verbally created, in order to enable their growth and competitiveness with economies from other continents. Science was to develop through investing in joint research. What do we have - the European Parliament, corporate EU parties and a system of imposing laws that are contrary to the adopted and still valid formulas for the protection of human rights were launched, trying to force their application through financial manipulation and institutional violence. The economy collapses when, instead of its development, its restrictions are financed with subsidies, falsehood is introduced under the guise of science, and Polish science is treated almost like a pariah of Europe, thanks to its own officials, who accepted, to mention only the fact of the points awarded to Polish scientific and so-called Western European publishers. Currently, the EU imposes laws on participating countries aimed at creating a dictatorship of technocrats, among others, through the right of officials to persecute society for critical assessments or statements [11].

Materials and Methods

Civilizational Incompetence

By adopting the initial criteria, four basic personality types were distinguished: 1. a well-mannered person, 2. a working person, 3. a playful person and 4. an active person 364 [12]. According to this theory, personality types are shaped by the roles required in social groups in which socialization takes place and which at the same time develop certain personal and creative tendencies. Three types of social groups were distinguished that shape specific personality types, in which individuals spend their childhood and youth: 1. educational, i.e. family or school, 2. work, i.e. farm, workshop, factory and 3. playing peers, also known as games.

A person living in society, during his life takes part in the functioning of many social groups, plays successively, and sometimes simultaneously, many different roles. Each of these three types in a different, specific way directs the later course of a person's life, develops personal and creative aspirations, and creates a completely separate biographical type.

The type of "well-mannered person" is formed, among others, in those who spent their childhood and youth under the influence of

long-term stay in school. Such a person has become accustomed to seeking positive evaluation and in life tries to strive for a good image through their behavior. They take into account the opinions of recognized authorities. They rely on the existence of a ready hierarchy of positions in which they occupy a specific place and can rise up the social ladder. They believe that they deserve a position and an economic position regardless of it. They profess the thesis according to which the world is rationally and planned ordered.

The type of "working man" was formed in people who, among other things, started working early and continue in it uninterruptedly, leaving no time for fun. The most important thing for this person is that for his work he receives an economic position that satisfies his needs at a level he accepts. He believes in the imperativeness of material factors in social life and as motivation for human action. Financial injustices are the most painful for them.

The "playful person" type is formed, among other things, under the influence of a group of peers from families that are sufficiently wealthy.

Three biographical varieties have been distinguished, depending on the type of games in which they participated most often or with the greatest interest: 1. social games, 2. political games, 3. warriors.³⁶⁵ What all three types of people have in common is the treatment of objective cultural systems as more or less interesting toys, objects that satisfy various spontaneous human aspirations, but have no other significance, in contrast to the issues of a person's social attitude to his or her own environment and the affairs of the group to which he or she belongs, which are considered important. "Politicians" shaped in this way may show great interest in exercising power, show gratitude and kindness towards people who supported them, and pay less attention to public affairs. "Warriors," when they have no outlet for their aspirations in war, seek it elsewhere, primarily in politics. The fourth type is the "active person."³⁶⁶ These are people who, among other things, belong to categories that deviate from the so-called "civilizational normality", i.e. not adapting to existing conditions, but moving away from the norms accepted in society. These deviations can be "under", i.e. a downward deviation, or "above", i.e. an upward deviation. What they have in common is opposition to the norms regulating their social roles, in particular to the functions imposed by the environment. In the active "under" there is nothing but a reluctance to personally adapt to the prevailing norms of human coexistence, on the contrary, he tries to break away from them as much as possible, to live freely, without effort, e.g. a criminal. The general attitude to life, the general biographical direction, decides whether a person is active. The average person, if he performs an act "under" or "above" normal, strives for normality. On the other hand, the active "under" has a constant tendency to oppose every order for his subjective freedom, while the active "above" has a constant tendency to transform all orders with which he comes into contact, all systems in which he participates. The "super" active person begins with an intention that he wants to achieve, although he anticipates that the current forces may not be sufficient, but recognizes that in the course of action new forces will appear that will make it possible to achieve it.

The "over" active personality focuses on tasks that are not imposed on him, but independently undertaken from various areas of cultural life, but most often he directs all his energy into the chosen field.

The source of the concept of personality types are social roles and cultural personality ideals that are internalized, causing stability of behavior and reactions to social situations. A special role in the formation of a specific personality type is played by the microstructures of society, i.e. social groups in which people grow up and live. The fundamental role is assigned to "wise" and "good" people [12].

A "wise" person is one who values diverse cultural systems, knows how to apply various tests of validity, and is positively interested in survival and development. A "good" person treats every person and the human community as a positive value.

It has been observed that the personality types formed in the previous system are of little use in creating a new order in Poland [12].

According to this theory, the so-called "civilizational incompetence" has been created, which consists of ingrained habits, reflexes, lack of skills necessary to use institutions, organizational forms, ways of life, technical devices that have been developed within the modern industrial civilization in Western countries. This "incompetence" has been caused, among others, by isolation from modern civilization and imposed institutional and organizational forms resulting from the principles of the system. Symptoms of this so-called "civilizational incompetence" include: 1. loss of work ethic, 2. discipline, 3. concern for quality, 4. disregard for the law, 5. dogmatism, 6. intolerance, 7. apparent actions, 8. predatory attitude towards nature, 9. egoism, 10. hostility, etc.

Another criterion for dividing individuals has become the distinct concept of personality, understood either as a set of relatively stable psychological features of an individual, distinguishing them from other people and giving stability to their behavior, or as a biological and psychological system defining human characteristics, determining the organization of their activities, psychological identity, direction and methods of adaptation to the environment and creative transformation of their environment [13]. The main components of this system are attitudes, beliefs, feelings, motives, needs, as well as intelligence, abilities and temperament. Personality is shaped in the course of development, on the basis of innate biophysical features, under the influence of external stimuli and one's own activity. There are many concepts of personality theory, e.g. in psychoanalysis it was assumed that personality consists of 3 systems: 1. "id", i.e. hereditary and innate psychological equipment, 2. "ego", i.e. a type of executive power to ensure the realization of the goals of the "id" and 3. "superego", i.e. internal representation of values and ideals, a type of internal moral arbiter. Personality is the result of the interaction of these 3 systems.

"Civilizational incompetence" is a term that can be understood as a lack or deficiency of competencies necessary to function in society, especially in the context of ongoing globalization

and technological development. This includes both a lack of knowledge and skills, as well as a lack of understanding of the principles of functioning of the modern world.

Civilizational incompetence and internalization of systemic rules: Internalization, internalization – a mechanism consisting in accepting externally imposed attitudes, views, norms and values as one's own. Civic competences: Lack of understanding of the principles of democracy, human rights, political and social processes. And this is how the current widespread civilizational incompetence is shaped.

Clicks

The individual in action is guided by diverse and multidirectional relations and reactions, causing counter-relations and counter-reactions from the environment. In a democratic system, the individual acts as a member of a team carrying out tasks for the common good, differentiated by the income obtained.

Joint actions are to guarantee the realization of recognized human rights and the satisfaction of the individual's own needs. Development is to allow for the expansion of the areas of both expected and established human rights and broadly understood individual's own needs. Phenomena assessed as negative in relation to the creation of law, implementation and implementation by public administration are noticed. This applies to both individuals who are public officials and teams constituting the executive, legislative and judicial branches.

This constitutes an interdisciplinary research challenge.

Pathology is understood as abnormal phenomena occurring in social life. A large number of individuals create a crowd "that thinks in images, and one image evokes in it a series of new images that are not logically connected with the first one. Ease in expressing judgments, opinions, taking a position in areas that often require erudition goes hand in hand with impulsiveness, irritability, susceptibility to manipulation. Changeability and exaggeration of feelings make the feelings of the crowd violent and extreme, that sympathy turns into adoration, and antipathy into hatred", this is also how parliamentarism works [14,15]. In Poland we have such wisdom "don't talk to an ignorant, at first he will bring you down to his level and then talk you over, thanks to his experience in this field".

A collective decision-maker generates threats, especially when it consists of people with a similar worldview, most often verbalized by belonging to political parties, which over time can transform into an extreme of a sectarian nature understood as a social group constituting a faction among the followers of some ideology. Here, negative actions and interactions occur, related to the individual, their qualified perception and the team associated with the loss of individual will independent of the knowledge and skills they possess, and over time, the negation of universally recognized, developed and legally established rules of conduct.

Research on security in management structures revealed and confirmed that the activity of so-called cliques has become a problem in Polish public life. They were distinguished as small,

informal groups often based on the use of the formal structure of an institution, enterprise, etc., characterized by: 1. a community of interests of members, 2. a goal of action that is contrary to the generally accepted system of values and norms, and 3. a desire to achieve benefits at the expense of others. Cliques are organized not only in the field of public life, they are known from history and the present, e.g. court, salon, social, small-town, etc. Research on their mechanism of operation in public and economic life has led to the demonstration of connections between the formal structure of an institution, office, workplace and the way in which the clique is organized and operated. It was established, among other things, that there is a relationship between the function performed in the place of employment and the task performed there. The possibility of unlawful action is determined by the place occupied in the service structure. The clique uses the existing structure of management and control in its activity. It has been observed that it makes extensive use of the existing system of official contacts. Various reasons decide about joining it.

Some of them are rooted in the position and role of the individual in the environment in which they formed. Analysis of materials concerning the activities of cliques shows that many people joined them in order not to offend people with whom they were associated in business, in order to gain their favor and support. Another group of reasons is rooted in the clique itself, its actions, methods of operation and their consequences.

Blackmail and threats are used to force people they care about to get involved in the activity. Based on the formal service structure, it usually gains significant power and wide possibilities of manipulating this structure to achieve its goals, e.g. by having influence on personnel decisions, dismissing inconvenient people from work, etc. The motive for their activity is most often economic profit, but it is not the only motive. Another one occurred, e.g. in activities occurring in creative environments, i.e. artistic or scientific. In this case, there were attempts to obtain undeserved benefits, i.e. honors, titles, authority, etc., achieved at the expense of the work and merits of the wronged people. In view of the author's 25 years of research on the phenomenon, a time dependency was established indicating a three-year period constituting the period of creation, consolidation and takeover of informal management in every social structure, except for family businesses. The next stage is the period after five years, when the clique takes over informal management and gives up the law in favor of its own agreements and customs. We see this especially in the activities of public offices at all levels, where the standard is changing the legal orientation to a contractual one through contacts using modern technology for the sake of exchanging information according to the rule "how do you do it?" and then unification in the broad sense. Officials mostly replace qualifications with the number of positions held on behalf of a long-term arrangement, giving up even basic forms of training, despite the fact that laws are currently changing and updating at an annual pace, especially taking into account public administration.

The generation of threats by the collective decision-maker gains strength due to the participation of individuals disturbed by childhood diseases, incurable ones, including dyslexia, Asperger's and autism, as well as psychopathy and sociopathy.

This leads, among other things, to the implementation of actions assigned to the will of the collective decision-maker in the form of government administration through statements by the executive in the public media constituting a form of verbal attack, imposing the will on society while bypassing the law and factual findings, thus threatening the health of the recipients of the messages and then enacting law that is contrary to the rules of the socio-political system to the detriment of society.

Power and Administrative Authority

Polish law creates a system in accordance with the theory of systems, according to which the essence comes down to treating the objects under study as open, understood in relation to law as branches of law, i.e. civil, criminal, etc. This means that the branches of law are a set of norms related in such a way that they constitute a new, distinctive whole. The aim of such a system is to implement a specific set of behaviors, in Poland being a consequence of the systemic rules contained in the Constitution. A set of legal norms can be considered a system if and only if it fulfills its main role, i.e. it organizes interpersonal and interstate relations normatively, in a way that satisfies society and the individual. The Polish legal system is shaped absolutely through the systemic rules included in the Constitution of the Republic of Poland and the sources of law indicated therein. The inconsistency of legal norms with the provisions of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland constitutes their invalidity by virtue of law itself, while the sources of law are also directly mentioned in the norm of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland. Public administration in Poland expresses the culture of security understood as material and intellectual activity and its products.

First of all, we refer to the content of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland in Article 4.1. The supreme power in the Republic of Poland belongs to the Nation. The concept of power means "the right to govern the state, as well as to govern members of the family, institutions or associations", here directly the right to govern the state [16].

Authority means "power over something", and using synonyms, superior is equivalent to superior. A nation, on the other hand, is "all the inhabitants of a given territory speaking one language, connected by a common past and culture, having common political and economic interests". To simplify, a nation is every resident of a state, born in it. On the other hand, public administration is all public institutions and officials in the state. In order to meet the systemic criterion, we also mention the concept of politician. According to the current definition, it is a member of a political party, whose source of income, both personal and family, is an amount paid from the funds of that party. This criterion means that all public officials, regardless of the level in the hierarchy occupied, at the moment of obtaining personal and family income from sources other than party funds, and mainly from the state budget, become public administration officials, rejecting the issue of politics. To sum up, every member of the Nation, i.e. in Poland, every Pole is, by operation of law, the superior of all officials, all levels of public administration in Poland, starting from the President of the Republic of Poland to the Councilor in the Commune, i.e. the smallest form of local government administration. This also directly concerns the

structural hierarchy of Judges and Parliamentarians, who de facto cannot be treated differently. However, despite this, the state and local good developed over generations has been assigned to the participation of citizens who do not constitute the authorities and are not superiors of public administration officials. The concept of authority placed in the records of public institutions has no reference to the factual or legal status.

Administration is a special form of management. As a concept, it comes from the combination of the Latin verb *ministeriè* – to serve, with the prefix *ad*, which strengthened the element of service or executive character; *administrare*, which meant to serve, and in time also to manage, or even to direct, but never to rule – *gubernare*, i.e. to make decisions in important matters [17].

From the perspective of civilization development, analyzing the phenomenon of power as preceding it and determining its nature, the concept of possession is noticed.

Before possession was legally exposed, we learn from excavations that the first people, the oldest in the sense of archaeologically revealed, left behind objects and drawings and descriptions regarding their use. They constituted their property and a form of trade. In a later period, from the era of the Roman Empire, possession becomes an institution of property law denoting a factual state, consisting in deciding and acting in accordance with the will of the possessor. The possessor has dominion over the thing, consisting in the possibility of doing whatever he wants with it. In Poland, the branch of civil law regulating the creation, content, change and termination of ownership rights and other rights to things is property law, which in the subjective sense corresponds to the following features: it is an absolute right, i.e. *effective erga omnes* - towards everyone; it concerns things.

The issues related to it are regulated by Book Two of the Civil Code entitled "Ownership and other property rights" and many special acts, e.g. the Act on Land and Mortgage Registers. A closed catalogue of property rights is characteristic of Polish law - the so-called *numerus clausus* principle of property rights: ownership, perpetual usufruct, usufruct, easement, pledge, mortgage, cooperative ownership right to premises. Extralegal possession is a concept meaning the actual power of a person over a thing in the "natural" sense of the word. According to the commonly prevailing view, the premises for determining the state of possession are: physical possession of the thing by the possessor (Latin *corpus possessionis*); the intention of the possessor to possess the thing as an owner (Latin *animus rem sibi habendi*). The lack of the second of the above-mentioned premises means that we are dealing with another legally significant state, namely possession, i.e. actual possession of a thing on behalf of someone else. Similarly, in administrative law, the concept of authority is distinguished, i.e. possession of competence, i.e. normatively distinguished, social permission to perform designated tasks, manage property. In the Polish Penal Code, the concept of theft is defined as taking possession of someone else's movable property for the purpose of its appropriation (Article 278 § 1 of the Penal Code) [18]. Taking possession means taking a thing out of someone else's possession and taking it into one's own possession. Authority over a thing

is a factual relationship, not a legal one, which means that it is possible to steal a thing that is held by a person who is not its owner, e.g. a possessor or a holder.

Analysis and reflection indicate that the aforementioned distortions in the use of the concept of "public authority" in the content of the Constitution were created intentionally during its creation in the years between 1995 and 1997, when the media were arguing about the content of the preamble, manipulating public opinion in order to divert attention from these provisions. This content has no coverage in the content of the Constitution or the laws and regulations, where all entities are assigned to the record of the power of the Nation, taking their content internally as administrative authority, limited only to constitutional and statutory competences and lower-ranking rights. This is why the established pathology in the formula of recognizing public authority - as authority in the sense of ownership, i.e. the possessor, and the rejection of the legal or correct option of public authority, the so-called administrative authority, i.e. statutory competences to carry out public activities, has come into common use. A connection is seen between the creators of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland, many of whom were not of Polish nationality. These legal anomalies became the starting point for the considerations in this study.

Methods

In the research process leading to writing this paper, many research methods were used, including one developed personally, scientifically reviewed and published [19]. To begin with, the methods used in the research process were divided into: observation; interview; organizational theory; analysis of scientific literature, written and electronic documentation; synthesis; scientific reflection; multi-dynamic interdisciplinary sensory-cognitive analytics.

Observation

The most elementary technique of empirical knowledge in social sciences is observation. It is a research activity consisting in collecting data (information) through observations, i.e. in their natural course and remaining within the direct range of vision and hearing of the researcher (observer).

Observation as a research technique is distinguished from ordinary observation in that it is purposeful, i.e. intentional and directed towards the systematic perception of the recognized object, process or phenomenon.

Interview

A very popular research technique in social sciences is the interview. It enables conscious learning about socio-political phenomena. An interview is a conversation between a researcher and a respondent or respondents according to previously developed instructions (or based on a special questionnaire). An interview is a process in which the researcher tries to influence the respondent by asking questions and persuading them to give statements on the subject being researched. This is one of the research techniques that enables the parallel use of observation

Organizational Theory

Organizational theory deals with detecting the regularity of the

process of subordinating individual actions to the goals of the whole; provides premises for showing the social context of the rationality of the actions of political entities, their external and internal conditions. The theory of organization is becoming a contemporary, relevant challenge of political life, determined by such political values as: 1. moving away from the repressive state, 2. autonomy of society towards the state, 3. decentralization and dispersion of administrative power, development of local government bodies, 4. participatory democracy, 5. activity and autonomy of minority groups, 6. tolerance towards different value systems, 7 self-organization, creation of informal groups, 8. general increase in the level of education, raising the level of political culture, 9. cultural syncretism, 10. replacing the philosophy of domination (over man, political institutions) with the idea of harmonious coexistence and partnership.

Analysis of Scientific Literature of Written and Electronic Documentation

Literature analysis in the research process consists of breaking down the recognized material into its component parts and considering (discussing) each part separately or mentally dividing it using logical abstraction. Analysis is often divided into: elementary, causal and logical. Elementary analysis occurs when the object of research is broken down into elements and no mutual relations are seen between them \neg . It is descriptive in nature. Causal analysis, also called functional analysis, aims to detect relations between individual phenomena. It consists of breaking down the object of research into its component parts, paying attention to the relations between them. It is usually preceded by elementary analysis. Logical analysis consists of breaking down complex cognitive objects into their component parts, taking into account the logical relations between them. Using library collections, in addition to specialist collections, general publications of an informative nature were used, which include encyclopedias, dictionaries, lexicons, reference books and reviewers. These publications are essential in the workshop of every researcher. Current access to electronic University libraries supported the research process. Access to electronic libraries on the PBN (Polish Scientific Library) websites was used; acade-mia.edu; scholar.google.com; Zenodo. Initially, in the analysis process, verification, selection, classification and categorization of literature were undertaken.

Synthesis

The term synthesis is understood as combining many different elements into one whole. Similar to analysis, synthesis is usually divided into: elementary, causal and logical. Elementary synthesis consists in creating a whole from individual elements; from various facts, phenomena, a typical selection (ideal type) is formulated, which is considered similar to all, and therefore can be considered representative of the whole. Causal synthesis is an important part; it is a specific reversal of analysis, it is also its specific test; mutual relations and relationships between elements of research are reduced to generalization.

Logical synthesis consists in combining component elements into a whole, taking into account the logical relations between them.

Scientific Reflection

Scientific reflection is the process of critically analyzing and

evaluating one's own knowledge, views, and experiences in a scientific context. It is a key element of intellectual development, allowing for a deeper understanding of a topic and improving research skills. In education, scientific reflection helps students and teachers connect new knowledge with previous experiences and build awareness of their own learning processes.

Multi-Dynamic Interdisciplinary Sensory-Cognitive Analytics

Multi-dynamic, i.e. multi - «multiple, multiple or a large amount of something» (here I recognize a multiplicity of diversified factors, initially most often impossible to determine), dynamic - 1) «mobile, elastic, elemental», 2) «arising, moved or occurring as a result of the action of forces», 3) «related to the intensity of the force of sounds» (here I recognize the diversity of movement shaped in a process with the participation of diversified factors, initially most often impossible to determine); 2. interdisciplinary, i.e. 1) «concerning two or more scientific disciplines», 2) «drawing on the achievements of several sciences»; 3. analytics, i.e. «science of the analysis of concepts and thoughts»; 4. sensory, i.e. «experienced through the senses» 5. cognitive, i.e. «acquiring knowledge about something, also: acquired knowledge». It is a diverse, multidirectional and multifactorial process in motion, using the achievements of many sciences that allow for the analysis of concepts and thoughts in order to acquire knowledge, the aim of which is to enable the solution of problems of a similar nature in similar conditions.

Results

Civilizational Incompetence

Referring to "civilizational incompetence", it is stated that it is primarily related to the lack of internalization of systemic rules in so-called countries with a democratic socio-political system by the entire society in such a way that they do not assimilate the applicable rules as their own, do not implement them in their personal, family and social life, disturbing the possible process of democratization of life and preventing its full implementation.

Clicks

Cliques in the process of functioning of public and private institutions, based on their own findings and assignment of the role of the so-called leader (here possible formal or informal), dismantle the institutional form by eliminating within a period of three years people who do not submit to them and then after five years they completely give up on the implementation of legal processes in favor of their routine or the routine of friends who have a similar function in other entities in accordance with the assumption "we do it as usual" or "how do you do it?". If the leaders are people with Asperger's syndrome, autism, psychopaths or sociopaths, i.e. a-social, they will introduce chaos in finances and great damage due to the lack of a sense of any responsibility while breaking numerous laws and not recognizing them in the implementation of tasks.

Power and Administrative Authority

The lack of distinction between the concepts of authority and administrative authority leads to the recognition of public assets earned at the national, regional and local government levels as one's own, and lower-level officials and all residents as their own and to dispose of them at their own discretion. In this way,

destroying the achievements of all generations, leading to social poverty, deprivation of public and private rights and even an attack on life and health, which took place in 2020-2023 under the guise of a pandemic.

Discussion

Civilizational Incompetence

The topic identified in Poland has its significant differences, described in detail in the content of the article. This issue has been discussed by the author since 2014, since the publication of the book entitled "Economic self-government. Poland-Europe-world", through at a later stage "Territorial government in Poland: tradition and contemporary political transformations" and "Grudziądz threats [20]. Identification, diagnosis, proposal of changes", in the content of which he refers to the subject content included in the publications of such authors as: Aristotle "Politics "; Blok Z [21]. "Systemic transformation in Poland", Długosz D. and Wygnański J. "Citizens co-decide: a guide to social participation"; Hopkin J. "European social democracy "; Sartori G. "The Theory of Democracy"; Soros G. "The Crisis of World Capitalism"; Toffler A. "Change of Power, Knowledge, Wealth, Violence at the Threshold of the 21st Century"; Znaniecki F. "People of today and the civilization of the future"; Dahl RA "Democracy and its critics" and many others [22-29]. The law in force in Poland, i.e. the Constitution of the Republic of Poland, the Act on Local Government; the Act on Public Finances and numerous Regulations and local law acts do not raise doubts [30]. They are confirmed by the analysis indicated both in the introduction and in the materials related to this issue and the results placed here. The polemic comes down to taking into account the opinions of the authors in the subject matter. All of them directly and indirectly confirm both the content of the listed provisions and the forecasts for the future developed by the authors in the results.

Clicks

Cliques have been known since time immemorial. They are formally registered organizations or informal ones; they can be found in both public administration entities and private administration entities. Over the course of history, they have appeared and continue to appear in all countries of the so-called Western civilization. In English-speaking countries, they sometimes take the form of lobbying clubs. Cliques are organized not only in the field of economic life, they are known from history and the present day, e.g. court, salon, social, small-town cliques, etc., and not all of them were criminal from the point of view of the law. In addition to the research conducted by the author, the following publications were taken into account: "Local political community and the issue of collective identity" edited by R. Piekarski; Jaroch W. "Crime in the processes of ownership transformation of state-owned enterprises"; Catanzaro D. "Motivations and emotions"; In Józef Piłsudski's view, "cliques" were primarily groups of people focused on their own interests, not the common good, which led to the dispersion of forces and the weakening of the state [31-33]. Piłsudski criticized them for their lack of patriotism, egoism and striving for power at the expense of national interests. Piłsudski saw "cliques" as a threat to the reconstruction and strengthening of the Polish state. He believed that rivalry and the struggle for influence within these groups prevented effective action for the common

good. He criticized the tendency to create "arrangements" and "arrangements" that would only aim to benefit their members, without taking into account the interests of the state. In his concept of a strong state based on the principles of justice and unity, "cliques" were seen as a destructive element that weakened the potential of the nation and the state. Piłsudski sought to build a state in which citizens were guided by the common good, not particular interests. The word "cliques" in the context of Piłsudski's views refers to a negative phenomenon related to the dispersion of forces, egoism and lack of patriotism, which had a detrimental effect on the development of the state [34]. Both the collected materials and the results obtained the same meaning in the matter of "Cliques" in the assessment not only of the authors mentioned here but also many others who were not indicated here in Japan, the USA, Italy; Germany; France and others.

Power and Administrative Authority

The issue of power and administrative authority is primarily a legal approach. Law in Poland shapes it both in the Constitution of the Republic of Poland and in acts such as the Civil Code; Family and Guardianship Code, which establish the concept of authority relating to ownership and possession, as well as administrative authority located in the complex of administrative law in Poland, understood as competences granted by law to decide on behalf of the National or Self-Government community in a strictly defined field and formula. Authors such as " A, B, C of territorial self-government" edited by B. Imiołczyk have spoken out in this matter; " Public Administration [35]. The System of Central State Administration. Commentary" edited by B. Szmulik and K. Miaskowska-Daszkiwicz; Bałaban A., "Polish systemic problems [36]. Constitution, sources of law, local government, human rights"; Bator A., Competences in law and jurisprudence; Garlicki L., "Polish constitutional law. Outline of the lecture"; " Constitutions of the Republic of Poland and commentary to the Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 1997" edited by Boć J.; " Civil Code. Commentary" Editors: prof. dr hab. Gniewek E., prof. dr hab. Machnikowski P.; Family and Guardianship Code. Commentary by dr hab. Gajda J., prof. UJK are only a selected part of the authors whose publications were used before the creation of this article [37-42]. Both the author of the text and the authors of the mentioned publications fully share the view regarding the social understanding and legal regulation of the issue of power and administrative authority with full understanding of their confusion and the pathology of the resulting herds.

Conclusions

Civilizational Incompetence

Conclusions regarding the lack of civilizational competences indicate a number of important issues that affect the individual development of an individual and collective reflection in the context of contemporary challenges. First of all, it should be emphasized that civilizational competences, as a set of skills and knowledge necessary for effective functioning in society, are the foundation for the sustainable development of individuals and societies. In the face of ongoing globalization, technologization and rapid social changes, the lack of these competences leads to the marginalization of individuals in the educational, professional and social context. Therefore, it becomes necessary to define key areas that require the intensification of educational

and social processes aimed at eliminating these gaps. Analysis of data on education, employment and social activity shows that individuals exposed to the lack of civilizational competences are often subject to exclusion, which leads to deepening social and economic differences. In addition, these people often show low awareness and are less involved in the life of local communities, which in turn weakens the social fabric. It is therefore crucial for educational policy and social institutions to cooperate in order to develop programs that not only provide technical knowledge, but also promote interpersonal skills, critical thinking and cooperation skills. In conclusion, the lack of civilizational competences is a complex problem that requires a multi-faceted approach. Actions are needed at the local and global level that will respond to the specific needs of societies and will also be able to adapt to dynamic conditions. The implementation of innovative educational programs that support the development of civilizational competences is necessary in order to achieve greater social integration and the activation of citizens. These actions should be based on constant analysis of changing conditions and needs, which will allow for more effective counteracting of exclusion and strengthening positive trends in communities. These conclusions imply the need for further research and analysis to ensure that the system is open to change and able to effectively respond to contemporary challenges.

Clicks

In the context of eliminating the so-called cliques, i.e. informal groups in society, the transformation processes analyzed in our previous chapters reveal complex challenges and potential strategies for action. One of the key conclusions is the need to understand the complexity of creating these groups and their roots in the social structure. Cliques often arise as a response to certain gaps in the formal system, and their elimination requires not only repressive actions, but above all the introduction of systemic reforms that can meet the real needs of their members. By providing alternatives in the form of institutionalized solutions, it is possible to effectively eliminate the motivations to create parallel structures. Another important aspect is to consider the impact of such initiatives on the broad social fabric. An approach based on stigmatization or marginalization of these groups can lead to the exacerbation of social conflicts, and in the long term does not bring the expected results. Therefore, it seems crucial to develop strategies that will not only eliminate cliques, but also focus on integrating their members into formal structures. For example, social, educational and professional support programs can play a fundamental role in the reintegration process, thus reducing the desire to belong to informal groups. Ultimately, eliminating cliques in society requires a holistic view of social problems and taking into account the needs of people who, for various reasons, feel a deficit in integration with formal institutions. This process can be effectively supported by the development of social policies based on cooperation between the public sector and civil society. By building trust and strengthening cooperation, it is possible to create the foundations for a healthier and more cohesive society that will successfully cope with the challenges posed by cliques. These conclusions indicate fundamental changes that should take the form of continuous dialogue and participation in order to effectively eliminate the social problems of all informal groups. These conclusions imply the need for further research and analysis to

ensure that the system is open to change and able to effectively respond to contemporary challenges.

Power and Administrative Authority

The final conclusions regarding improving the knowledge of public and civil rights in Poland emphasize the importance of a systematic and comprehensive approach to civic education. In the face of the dynamically changing political and social context, understanding legal regulations and the principles of functioning of public institutions is becoming important for every citizen. Civic education is not only knowledge of rights and obligations, but also the ability to think critically and actively participate in social life. Therefore, it is important that educational programs, both in primary and secondary schools and at universities, contain not only theoretical aspects of law, but also practical applications that help shape conscious citizens. One of the important elements of effective education in the field of public and civil rights is the use of modern teaching methods and tools. Integration of information technology in curricula, organization of debates, simulations and practical workshops allows for the involvement of students in the learning process. Such an education model promotes better information absorption and development of skills in analyzing and assessing social situations. Additionally, cooperation with non-governmental organizations and public institutions can enrich educational programs with real experiences and projects that promote civic activity. From the final perspective, it is advisable for actions to improve the knowledge of public and civil rights to be interactive and to be adapted to the diverse needs of local communities. Examples of effective initiatives show how important cooperation between different segments of society is, including schools, non-governmental organizations and local government institutions. Only through an integrated approach can we achieve real improvement in the understanding of public rights, which will consequently lead to greater civic activity and thus to strengthening the democratic foundations of society. These conclusions imply the need for further research and analysis so that the education system in Poland remains coherent, open to change and able to effectively respond to the challenges of modern times.

Authors' Contributions

Dr. Slawomir Stanislaw Dębski: Conceptualization

1. Resources
2. Data collection
3. Software
4. Formal analysis
5. Supervision
6. Fundraising
7. Validation
8. Investigation
9. Imaging
10. Methodology
11. Writing - Original Draft
12. Project Administration
13. Writing - Review and Editing

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Conflicts of Interest

"The author declares no conflict of interest."

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